
EFFECT OF ULTRASOUND CAVITATION AND RADIOFREQUENCY VERSUS HIGH-INTENSITY INTERVAL TRAINING EXERCISE ON MEAN PLATELET VOLUME IN PATIENTS WITH METABOLIC SYNDROME

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Abstract**Background & Aims**

Metabolic syndrome is a multifactorial disease with multiple manifestations include abdominal obesity, hypertension, hyperglycemia, hypertriglyceridemia and reduced high-density lipoprotein cholesterol (HDL-C). Ultrasonic Cavitation (UC) and radiofrequency (RF) are FDA-approved devices for local obesity reduction. High-intensity interval training (HIIT) is time saving exercise for improvement of metabolic health. Mean platelet volume (MPV) is a potential marker of platelet activity. Higher MPV is observed in patients with abdominal obesity, diabetes mellitus, hypertension and hypercholesterolemia.

Objectives: The purpose of this research was to compare between the effect of combined ultrasound cavitation and radiofrequency versus HIIT exercise on anthropometric indices in centrally obese MetS patients, confirm the association between MPV and the risk factors of development of cardiovascular disease such as body mass index (BMI), waist circumference, dyslipidemia, hypertension and insulin resistance, measure the effect of abdominal fat reduction on MPV as a biomarker for cardiovascular risk and measure the effect of abdominal fat reduction on lipid profile and insulin resistance in centrally obese MetS patients.

Materials and methods: randomized controlled clinical trial, 40 patients diagnosed with metabolic syndrome having abdominal obesity were randomly divided into two equal groups (group A & B). All patients were instructed to go on a balanced hypo-caloric diet through the study period (8 weeks). Patients of group A was treated using ultrasound cavitation combined with radiofrequency using Mable 6 Duo Ultra cavitation + Multipolar radiofrequency system, one session per week for eight weeks (8 sessions). Patients of group B were on HIIT exercise for 8 weeks (three sessions per week). Assessment was done for both groups at day one and follow up after 8 weeks by clinical and laboratory measures.

Results: Both groups showed a highly significant improvement in clinical assessment parameters (P value <0.001) including waist circumference, weight, waist to hip ratio (WHR), BMI, skin fold thickness, abdominal fat range, body fat Percentage, and blood pressure (SBP & DBP) and laboratory assessment parameters including MPV, lipid profile, fasting glucose, fasting insulin and Homeostatic Model Assessment for Insulin Resistance (HOMA-IR) (except LDL in group B there was a non-significant improvement (P value 0.080). On comparing group A and group B, there

was more prominent reduction in waist circumference, WHR, skin fold thickness, abdominal fat range in group A than B. However, there was more prominent reduction in weight, BMI, body fat percent, systolic & diastolic blood pressure (SBP &DBP), MPV, cholesterol, fasting glucose, insulin and HOMA-IR in group B than group A. Also, the study confirmed positive correlation between MPV and all those risk factors before and after treatment in both groups.

Conclusions: This study supports that combined UC & RF sessions are very effective in reducing abdominal obesity and improvement in other MetS variables such as dyslipidemia, hyperglycemia, hypertension and insulin resistance. However, HIIT exercise was superior in improving total body weight, total body fat, BMI and superior in improving blood pressure, MPV, cholesterol level, blood glucose and insulin resistance more than combined UC &RF.

Key words: Metabolic syndrome, Ultrasound cavitation, Radiofrequency, HIIT, MPV

1 INTRODUCTION

Metabolic syndrome (MetS) is a multifactorial disease with multiple risk factors that arises from insulin resistance and adipose tissue dysfunction with abnormal deposition (1). It is considered a risk factor for coronary heart disease, as well as diabetes, fatty liver. The clinical manifestations of this syndrome may include hypertension, hyperglycemia, hypertriglyceridemia, reduced high-density lipoprotein cholesterol (HDL-C), and abdominal obesity (2).

Although the etiology for metabolic syndrome remains unclear (3), there are two forces that have implicated in the spread of metabolic syndrome which are the increased availability and consumption of high calorie-low fiber fast food and decreased physical activity because of sedentary lifestyles and mechanized transportation (4).

There are several mechanisms for the pathophysiology of MetS, and the most widely accepted of these is insulin resistance with fatty acid excess as a consequence of inappropriate lipolysis. Other mechanisms involved in development of MetS include genetics and epigenetics, pancreatic β -cell dysfunction, obesity and lipid Toxicity, oxidative stress and glucose toxicity, chronic inflammation, circadian rhythm, gut microbiota and dietary effects (5).

Metabolic disorders such as dyslipidemia, obesity, and elevated blood pressure and glucose are risk factors for cardiovascular diseases that lead to prothrombotic tendency and platelet hyperactivation (6).

Currently the changes in MPV can be considered and used as a marker in various inflammatory diseases. Hyperactivity of blood platelets markedly increases susceptibility of patients to acute cardiac incidents. Large and reactive platelets increase the risk of thrombus formation because it has greater amount of cell granules, higher expression of adhesion molecules, and undergoes faster activation, which results in platelet hyperactivity and increased risk of clot formation (7).

Management of MetS involves a combination of life style modification and pharmacological interventions. Life style modifications, including dietary control and physical activity which are important for regulation of all components of MetS resulting in decreased weight, blood pressure, triglycerides, and fasting glucose levels and raising HDL cholesterol levels (8,9).

High-intensity interval training (HIIT) is defined as an intermittent style of exercise training involving short bursts of high-intensity exercise, for example, intermittent exercise that achieves $\geq 90\%$ of maximal heart rate (HR) separated by periods of recovery or rest (10,11). This exercise model has been ranked number 1 in the health and fitness trends in 2018 due to its time-saving nature (12,13). The beneficial impact of HIIT on metabolic health is improving vascular and cardiorespiratory fitness, fat loss, insulin sensitivity, and reducing diabetes risk (14,15)

Ultrasonic Cavitation (UC) and radiofrequency (RF) are FDA approved devices for local adiposity reduction. Ultrasonic waves generate compression cycles that exert positive and negative pressure. This pushing and pulling effect can crack the fat cells. Ultrasonic energy within the deeper fat layers causes cavities in the fat cell that reduces the overall thickness of the adipose layer. The mechanical acoustic effects of ultrasound cavitation caused selective fat cell disruption without causing injury to skin, vessels, nerves or connective tissue (16).

The mechanism of the therapeutic effect of RF is via increasing the flow of the local blood supply to the adipose tissue. Also, RF cause contraction of collagen fibers, remodeling of connective tissue and activation of fibroblast (17, 18).

2 SUBJECTS AND METHODS

2.1 Study design and subjects

A randomized controlled study was carried out on forty patients with age ranged from 30 to 55 years old diagnosed with metabolic syndrome and showed abdominal obesity. They were selected according to the American Heart Association and the National Heart Lung and Blood Institute in 2005 (19) as they denoted that metabolic syndrome is present if the patients showed three or more of the following criteria.

Metabolic syndrome is present if three or more of the following criteria are met.

1- Abdominal obesity: ≥ 102 cm (>40 inches) in males

≥ 88 cm (>35 inches) in females

2- Raised triglyceride levels: ≥ 150 mg/dL

3- Reduced HDL levels: < 40 mg/dL in men and < 50 mg/dL

in women

4- Raised BP: ≥ 130 mm Hg systolic or ≥ 85 mm Hg diastolic

5- Raised fasting glucose levels: ≥ 100 mg/dL.

All the patients were fulfilling the criteria number 1.

Exclusion Criteria: The following patients were excluded from this study:

1-Patients with malignancies.

2- Pregnant women.

3-Patients with history of medical illnesses such as chronic liver and/or renal diseases, alcohol consumption and smoking.

4- Patients with history of implantation of a pacemaker device.

5-Women with sensitivity to light, anemia.

6-Diseases cause hypercholesterolemia such as nephrotic syndrome, hypothyroidism, Cushing's syndrome and using medication interfere with lipid metabolism such as glucocorticoids, retinoic acid, antipsychotics anticonvulsants .

7-Any manifestation of of cardiorespiratory diseases detected by history or clinical examination.

8-Patients with history of hernia surgery.

Ain Shams medical ethics committee authorized the trial. Patients who consented to participate in the research and completed the eligibility requirements were given a general description of it before they signed an informed consent form.

Patients were divided into two equal groups randomly (group A & B). Patients of group A was treated using UC combined with RF using Mable 6 Duo Ultra cavitation and Multipolar RF system, one session per week for eight weeks (8 sessions). Patients of group B were on high intensity interval training exercise for 8 weeks (three sessions per week). Assessment was done for both groups at day one and follow up after 8 weeks by clinical and laboratory measures.

2.2 Calculating the sample size

The community and public health department of the college of medicine at Ain Shams University, under the direction of a statistics specialist, established the sample size.

Using PASS 11 program for sample size calculation, sample size was 20 patients per group which can detect the difference between 2 groups with power 80% and x-error 0.05.

2.3 Clinical and laboratory assessment:

A-Clinical assessment:

1-Measurement of waist circumference:

Waist circumference was measured at the midpoint between the lower margin of least palpable rib and the top of the iliac crest.

2-Waist-to-hip ratio (WHR) measurement

3- Body mass index (BMI)

4-Skin fold measurement: Subject was assessed by taking a fold of skin at waist (Suprailiac) region fat using baseline skin fold caliper.

5-Complete body analysis: Complete diagnostic scale will be used to estimate body composition information such as body fat percentage, abdominal (visceral) fat, body water percentage, and muscle mass.

6-Measurement of Blood Pressure

B- Laboratory assessment:**1-Measurement of mean platelet volume:**

Measured in EDTA tube by full automated analyzer.

2-Lipid profile: Total serum cholesterol (TC), low-density lipoprotein cholesterol (LDL-C), high-density lipoprotein cholesterol (HDL-C) and triglyceride (TG),

Total cholesterol: HDL ratio: Marker for risk of heart diseases

3-HOMA-IR equation: widely used to estimate insulin resistance which uses fasting blood level.

Its equation is $HOMA-IR = (\text{glucose in mmol/L} \times \text{insulin in mIU/mL}) / 22.5$ (20).

2.4 Study interventions

All patients were instructed to go on a balanced hypo-caloric diet through the study period (8 weeks) that provided 1500 to 1800 kcal daily. It was low in fat (20% to 25%), high in complex carbohydrate (50% to 60%), and sufficient in protein (25% to 30%). The patients were divided into two groups randomly:

Group A :

Patients of group A was treated using UC combined with RF using Mable6 Duo Ultra cavitation and Multipolar RF system. Each session 30 minutes (15 minute each side of abdomen). Prior to the treatment , patients advised to stop smoking and drinking alcohol for a few days, avoid dehydrating activities and caffeine and advised to drink at least 8-10 glasses of water 2-3 days prior to and post the treatment. Also, avoid using aspirin, ibuprofen or other anti-inflammatory products for 2 days prior and after treatment.

Group B :

Patients of group B were on high intensity interval training exercise for 8 weeks (three sessions per week).

HIIT protocol:

Consists of :

- Warm up : 5 minutes (60 % of Maximum Heart rate (HRmax))
- Bout number:10 sets
- Bout duration: 1 minute
- Modality: running on treadmill
- Work intensity: 80-90% of HRmax
- Recovery period: 1 minute (active recovery : walking on treadmill) (60-70% of HRmax)
- Cool down: 5 minutes (60 % of HRmax)

Blood pressure and pulse was measured before, during and after the session. Good hydration is important before and after the session.

2.5 Statistical analysis

The collected data was revised, coded, tabulated and introduced to a PC using Statistical package for Social Science (SPSS 25). Data was presented and suitable analysis was done according to the type of data obtained for each parameter.

i. Descriptive statistics:

1. Mean, Standard deviation (\pm SD) for numerical data.
2. Frequency and percentage of non-numerical data.

ii. Analytical statistics:

1. Student T Test was used to assess the statistical significance of the difference between two study group means.
2. Fisher's exact test: was used to examine the relationship between two qualitative variables when the expected count is less than 5 in more than 20% of cells
3. Paired t-test was used to assess the statistical significance of the difference between two means measured twice for the same study group
4. Correlation analysis (using Pearson's method): To assess the strength of association between two quantitative variables. The correlation coefficient denoted symbolically "r" defines the strength (magnitude) and direction (positive or negative) of the linear relationship between two variables.
 - $r=0-0.19$ is regarded as very weak correlation
 - $r=0.2-0.39$ as weak correlation
 - $r=0.40-0.59$ as moderate correlation
 - $r=0.6-0.79$ as strong correlation
 - $r=0.8-1$ as very strong correlation

2.6 Ethics

The medical faculty of Ain Shams University's Ethical Committee gave its approval for the current research.

3 RESULTS

40 patients age ranged from 30-44 years, 36 patients (90 %) were females and 4 patients (10%) were males. All patients completed the treatment all through the study with no dropouts. Both groups age and sex matched, there were non- statistically significant difference between group A&B regarding all demographic and medical data as shown in table 1

Table 1: Comparison between group A & group B regarding demographic and medical data:

		Group A	Group B	t test		
		Mean \pm SD	Mean \pm SD	T	p value	sig.
Age (years)	Mean \pm SD	36.15 \pm 4.61	36.1 \pm 4.23	0.04	0.972	NS
	Range	30 – 44	30 – 44			

Age of onset of obesity (years)	Mean±SD	18.45 ± 6.1	18.75 ± 5.51	-0.16	0.871	NS
	Range	10 – 35	10 – 30			
Duration of disease (years)	Mean±SD	14.7 ± 4.34	14.15 ± 4.43	0.40	0.694	NS
	Range	7 – 21	7 – 22			
				test of sig.		
		N (%)	N (%)	Value	p value	sig.
Sex	Male	2 (10%)	=2 (10%)	Fisher exact test	1.000	NS
	Female	18 (90%)	18 (90%)			
Occupation	No	9 (45%)	7 (35%)	X ² =0.42	0.519	NS
	Yes	11 (55%)	13 (65%)			
Activity level	lightly active	9 (45%)	7 (35%)	X ² =0.42	0.519	NS
	Sedentary	11 (55%)	13 (65%)			
Smoking	No	10 (50%)	10 (50%)	Fisher exact test	1.000	NS
	Passive	8 (40%)	7 (35%)			
	Yes	2 (10%)	3 (15%)			
Symptoms of hyperglycemia	No	16 (80%)	16 (80%)	Fisher exact test	1.000	NS
	Yes	4 (20%)	4 (20%)			
Family history of obesity	No	3 (15%)	2 (10%)	Fisher exact test	1.000	NS
	Yes	17 (85%)	18 (90%)			
Acanthosis Nigricans	No	15 (75%)	14 (70%)	X ² =0.13	0.723	NS
	Yes	5 (25%)	6 (30%)			
Xanthelasma	No	19 (95%)	19 (95%)	Fisher exact test	1.000	NS
	Yes	1 (5%)	1 (5%)			
Peripheral neuropathy	No	6 (30%)	7 (35%)	X ² =0.11	0.736	NS
	Yes	14 (70%)	13 (65%)			

P-value>0.05: Non –significant (NS); P-value<0.05: Significant (S); P-value<0.01: highly significant (HS)

Group A:

There was a highly statistically significant improvement (P value <0.001) in all clinical parameters (except skeletal muscle mass (SMM) showed non-significant change) and laboratory assessment parameters in group A after combined UC & RF sessions as shown in table 2 &3.

Table 2: Comparison between Clinical assessment of group A before and after treatment:

Group A	Day one		After 8 weeks		t test		
	Range	Mean ± SD	Range	Mean± SD	t	P value	sig.
Waist circumference (cm)	97 – 130	114.40 ± 9.12	88 – 118.5	104.05 ±8.83	49.59	<0.001	HS
Weight (kg)	85 – 126	101.25 ± 9.90	80.5 – 119.1	95.62 ± 9.84	26.45	<0.001	HS
WHR	0.87 – 1.1	0.97 ± 0.06	0.8 – 1.02	0.89 ±0.06	43.06	<0.001	HS

BMI (kg/m ²)	35.4 – 46.8	39.78 ± 3.26	33.5 – 44.2	37.57 ± 3.29	24.24	<0.001	HS
Skin fold thickness (mm)	28 – 50	42.20 ± 6.39	20 – 42	32.45 ± 5.95	34.85	<0.001	HS
Abdominal fat range	26 – 38.2	33.31 ± 3.32	19.7 – 31.5	26.34 ± 3.17	55.52	<0.001	HS
Body fat Percentage%	35 – 54.2	46.46 ± 5.73	32.7 – 51.2	43.83 ± 5.76	35.00	<0.001	HS
skeletal muscle mass (kg)	25 – 34.2	31.24 ± 2.39	25.1 – 34.2	31.25 ± 2.37	-1.45	0.163	NS
Systolic blood pressure (mmHg)	119 – 140	135.55 ± 5.92	116 – 137	131.40 ± 5.58	22.84	<0.001	HS
Diastolic blood pressure (mmHg)	70 – 90	83.70 ± 6.33	68 – 89	81.80 ± 6.28	27.61	<0.001	HS

P-value>0.05: Non –significant (NS); P-value<0.05: Significant (S); P-value<0.01: highly significant (HS) *WHR: waist to hip ratio, BMI (body mass index)

Table 3: Comparison between laboratory assessment of group A before and after of treatment:

Group A	Day one		After 8 weeks		Paired t test		
	Range	Mean ± SD	Range	Mean ± SD	t	p value	sig.
MPV (fL)	9 – 11.9	10.69 ± 0.82	8.7 – 11.4	10.20 ± 0.79	13.57	<0.001	HS
Cholesterol (mg/dL)	160 – 210	189.45 ± 14.98	156 – 204	183.50 ± 14.43	18.58	<0.001	HS
TG (mg/dL)	155 – 179	168.05 ± 6.96	127 – 173	159.70 ± 9.88	5.04	<0.001	HS
LDL (mg/dL)	96 – 156	128.86 ± 17.75	93 – 150	124.23 ± 17.41	18.28	<0.001	HS
HDL (mg/dL)	36 – 48	40.45 ± 3.93	36 – 49	42.55 ± 3.78	-10.30	<0.001	HS
Cholesterol: HDL ratio	3.3 – 5.8	4.72 ± 0.80	3.1 – 5.6	4.32 ± 0.72	10.46	<0.001	HS
Fasting glucose (mg/dL)	100 – 127	115.80 ± 7.53	95 – 120	108.65 ± 7.26	23.05	<0.001	HS
Fasting insulin (mIU/L)	8.8 – 14.8	12.52 ± 1.68	6.5 – 12.9	10.19 ± 1.76	31.67	<0.001	HS
HOMA-IR	2.1 – 4.5	3.54 ± 0.69	1.5 – 3.8	2.72 ± 0.66	25.77	<0.001	HS

P-value>0.05: Non –significant (NS); P-value<0.05: Significant (S); P-value<0.01: highly significant (HS) *Mean platelet volume (MPV), Triglyceride (TG), Low-density lipoprotein (LDL), High-density lipoprotein (HDL) & HOMA-IR (Homeostatic Model Assessment for Insulin Resistance)

Group B:

There was a highly statistically significant improvement (P value <0.001) in group B in all clinical and laboratory assessment parameters after HIIT exercise sessions except LDL showed non-significant change as shown in table 4 & 5.

Table 4: Comparison between Clinical assessment of group B before and after treatment:

Group B	Day one		After 8 weeks		Paired t test		
	Range	Mean ± SD	Range	Mean ± SD	t	p value	sig.
Waist circumference(cm)	97 – 129	113.13 ± 9.07	92 – 122.5	106.63 ± 8.51	31.68	<0.001	HS
Weight (kg)	88.5 – 124	101.80 ± 8.38	81.5 – 115.3	93.38 ± 8.18	40.43	<0.001	HS

WHR	0.87 – 1.09	0.96 ± 0.06	0.84 – 1.04	0.92 ± 0.05	23.97	<0.001	HS
BMI(kg/m ²)	35.5 – 46.7	39.45 ± 3.03	32.7 – 43.5	36.15 ± 2.81	30.25	<0.001	HS
Skin fold thickness (mm)	30 – 50	41.70 ± 6.19	25 – 43	34.85 ± 5.45	25.91	<0.001	HS
Abdominal fat range	27 – 38	33.01 ± 3.30	23 – 33.2	28.25 ± 3.05	52.30	<0.001	HS
Body fat Percentage	35.7 – 54.1	47.21 ± 4.67	32.4 – 49.9	43.19 ± 4.52	38.39	<0.001	HS
skeletal muscle mass (kg)	25.1 – 34.2	31.66 ± 2.09	25.5 – 35.2	32.58 ± 2.21	- 16.57	<0.001	HS
Systolic blood pressure (mmHg)	120 – 140	135.25 ± 5.84	111 – 130	125.00 ± 5.39	63.99	<0.001	HS
Diastolic blood pressure (mmHg)	70 – 90	83.75 ± 6.41	70 – 84	78.05 ± 5.47	17.10	<0.001	HS

P-value>0.05: Non –significant (NS); P-value<0.05: Significant (S); P-value<0.01: highly significant (HS) *WHR: waist to hip ratio , BMI (body mass index)

Table 5: Comparison between laboratory assessment of group B before and after treatment:

Group B	Day one		After 8 weeks		Paired t test		
	Range	Mean ±SD	Range	Mean ±SD	T	p value	sig.
MPV (fL)	9.2 – 11.8	10.67 ±0.80	8.6 – 10.8	9.67 ±0.68	21.53	<0.001	HS
Cholesterol (mg/dL)	161 – 210	188.15 ±15.16	156 – 202	180.15 ±14.00	19.49	<0.001	HS
TG (mg/dL)	155 – 178	167.15 ±7.02	102 – 171	157.45 ±14.32	3.94	0.001	HS
LDL (mg/dL)	98.2 – 155	128.01 ±17.31	94 – 149	123.38 ±16.67	1.85	0.080	NS
HDL(mg/dL)	36 – 47	40.70 ± 4.12	38 – 48	42.55 ±3.66	-11.10	<0.001	HS
Cholesterol: HDL ratio	3.4 – 5.8	4.66 ± 0.82	3.2 – 5.3	4.24± 0.69	11.44	<0.001	HS
Fasting glucose (mg/dL)	102 – 126	115.00 ± 7.23	93 – 114	103.00 ±5.96	21.72	<0.001	HS
Fasting insulin (mIU/L)	10 – 14.6	12.42 ± 1.63	7.8 – 12.8	9.98±1.45	19.84	<0.001	HS
HOMA-IR	2.4 – 4.5	3.50 ±0.67	1.6 – 3.6	2.51 ±0.55	18.80	<0.001	HS

P-value>0.05: Non –significant (NS); P-value<0.05: Significant (S); P-value<0.01: highly significant (HS) *Mean platelet volume (MPV), Triglyceride (TG), Low-density lipoprotein (LDL), High-density lipoprotein (HDL) & HOMA-IR (Homeostatic Model Assessment for Insulin Resistance)

Comparison between group A and group B:

There was non- statistically significant difference between group A and group B regarding clinical and laboratory assessment parameters at day one.

There was a highly statistically significant difference (P value <0.001) between group A & B regarding mean value of reduction in waist circumference, weight, WHR, BMI, skin fold thickness, abdominal fat range, body fat Percentage, and in blood pressure (systolic & diastolic) after 8 weeks of treatment as shown in table 6, Figure 1.

There was more prominent reduction in waist circumference, WHR, skin fold thickness and abdominal fat range in group A than group B. However, there was more prominent reduction in weight, BMI, body fat percent and SBP & DBP in group B than group A. There was also, higher increase in skeletal muscle mass in group B more than group A.

Table 6: Comparison between group A and group B as regard difference in the mean value of clinical assessment parameters before & after treatment:

Clinical assessment	Group A	Group B	t test		
	Difference in the Mean value \pm SD	Difference in the Mean value \pm SD	t	p value	sig.
Waist circumference reduction(cm)	10.35 \pm 0.93	6.50 \pm 0.92	13.15	<0.001	HS
Weight reduction (kg)	5.64 \pm 0.95	8.42 \pm 0.93	-9.33	<0.001	HS
WHR reduction	0.08 \pm 0.01	0.04 \pm 0.01	13.64	<0.001	HS
BMI reduction (kg/m ²)	2.21 \pm 0.41	3.30 \pm 0.49	-7.64	<0.001	HS
Skin fold thickness reduction (mm)	9.75 \pm 1.25	6.85 \pm 1.18	7.53	<0.001	HS
Abdominal fat range reduction	6.98 \pm 0.56	4.76 \pm 0.41	14.28	<0.001	HS
Body fat Percentage reduction	2.63 \pm 0.34	4.03 \pm 0.47	-10.86	<0.001	HS
skeletal muscle mass (kg) increase	0.01 \pm 0.03	0.92 \pm 0.25	-16.26	<0.001	HS
Systolic blood pressure reduction (mmHg)	4.15 \pm 0.81	10.25 \pm 0.72	-25.18	<0.001	HS
diastolic blood pressure reduction (mmHg)	1.90 \pm 0.31	5.70 \pm 1.49	-11.17	<0.001	HS

P-value>0.05: Non –significant (NS); P-value<0.05: Significant (S); P-value<0.01: highly significant (HS) *WHR: waist to hip ratio , BMI (body mass index)

Figure 1: Comparison between group A and group B as regard difference in the mean value of clinical assessment parameters before & after treatment.

There was a highly statistically significant difference between group A & B regarding mean value of reduction in MPV, cholesterol, fasting glucose (P value <0.001) and in HOMA-IR (P value 0.007). There was a more prominent reduction in group B than group A.

However, There was a non- statistically significant difference between group A & B regarding mean difference in TG reduction (P value 0.652), LDL reduction (P value 0.998), HDL increase (P value 0.348), Cholesterol: HDL ratio reduction (P value 0.780) and fasting insulin reduction (P value 0.470) as shown in table 7 & figure 2.

Table 7: Comparison between group A and group B as regard difference in the mean value of laboratory assessment parameters before & after treatment:

Laboratory assessment	Group A	Group B	t test		
	Difference in the Mean value ± SD	Difference in the Mean value ± SD	t	p value	sig.
MPV reduction (fL)	0.49 ± 0.16	1.00 ± 0.21	-8.79	<0.001	HS

Cholesterol reduction (mg/dL)	5.95 ± 1.43	8.00 ± 1.84	-3.94	<0.001	HS
TG reduction (mg/dL)	8.35 ± 7.41	9.70 ± 11.00	-0.46	0.652	NS
LDL reduction (mg/dL)	4.63 ± 1.13	4.63 ± 11.18	0.00	0.998	NS
HDL increase (mg/dL)	2.10 ± 0.91	1.85 ± 0.75	0.95	0.348	NS
Cholesterol: HDL ratio reduction	0.41 ± 0.17	0.42 ± 0.16	-0.28	0.780	NS
Fasting glucose reduction (mg/dL)	7.15 ± 1.39	12.00 ± 2.47	-7.65	<0.001	HS
Fasting insulin reduction(mIU/L)	2.34 ± 0.33	2.44 ± 0.55	-0.73	0.470	NS
HOMA-IR reduction	0.82 ± 0.14	0.99 ± 0.24	-2.88	0.007	HS

P-value>0.05: Non –significant (NS); P-value<0.05: Significant (S); P-value<0.01: highly significant (HS) *Mean platelet volume (MPV), Triglyceride (TG), Low-density lipoprotein (LDL), High-density lipoprotein (HDL) & HOMA-IR (Homeostatic Model Assessment for Insulin Resistance)

Figure 2: Comparison between group A and group B as regard difference in the mean value of laboratory assessment parameters before & after treatment.

Correlations:

- There was a highly statistically significant positive correlation between MPV and waist circumference, weight, WHR, BMI, skin fold thickness, abdominal fat range, body fat Percentage

systolic blood pressure, diastolic blood pressure, cholesterol, TG, LDL, Cholesterol: HDL ratio, fasting glucose, fasting insulin and HOMA-IR. It also shows a highly statistically significant negative correlation between MPV and HDL before and after treatment in all patients. It means that MPV can be a diagnostic and prognostic biomarker for all these risk factors and useful in longitudinal studies.

- There was a highly statistically significant positive correlation between abdominal fat reduction and reduction of MPV, cholesterol, Cholesterol: HDL ratio, fasting glucose, fasting insulin, HOMA-IR and HDL increase in both groups.

4. DISCUSSION

Anthropometric values like waist circumference, WHR, abdominal fat range and skin fold thickness measured during our study showed a statistically highly significant improvement (reduction) in both groups ($P < 0.001$). This reduction in group A is in accordance with other studies like Kapoor et al. 2017, Safari Bidokhti et al. 2019 and Abdel-Aal et al. 2022 (21, 22, 23).

Studies that used only one modality UC, reported less reduction in waist circumference than our results (24, 25). Also, Assim's Study that used each modality separately as UC group & RF group showed less reduction in WHR and abdominal fat percentage in each group than our study results (26). This is also in agreement with Farag et al. 2021 and Abotaleb et al. 2019 studies that used only UC showed reduction in visceral fat range (VFR) and in percent of reduction of abdominal fat respectively but their reduction was less than our results because we used the two modalities (UC & RF) as well as our patients followed a balanced hypo-caloric diet (27, 28).

Previous study results affirmed that the mixture of UC treatment and low-calorie diet results in a higher productivity than a low-calorie diet alone in bringing down the anthropometric, complete body arrangement and plasma lipoprotein factors (29).

The combined therapy named 'ultrafrequency' promotes synergistic effect on reduction of adiposity as UC facilitates lipolysis. Then RF immediately propels intercellular fat content to lymphatic circulation by heating and improving circulation. On the other hand, a low-calorie diet prevents the body from receiving more fat (18, 22).

The reduction in group B is in concordance with results of a study by Hyun in 2021 that showed also a statistically significant reduction in waist circumference, visceral fat level and skin fold thickness after HIIT exercise program (30).

Several meta-analysis reported that HIIT exercise was effective in reducing the abdominal visceral fat area (-6.8 cm^2), waist circumference (approximately -2.3 cm), WHR (-0.01), abdominal fat mass and visceral fat mass. Also Wewege et al. 2017 observed a significant effect of HIIT with a waist circumference reduction approximately 3 cm, while Batacan et al. 2017 found a reduction only in an extended intervention (>12 weeks) with a decrease approximately 2 cm (10, 31, 32).

On comparing group A and group B, results revealed statistically highly significant difference ($P < 0.001$) between mean value of reduction as regards waist circumference, abdominal fat range,

skin fold thickness and WHR. The reduction was more prominent in group A than group B, which means that combined UC & RF sessions were more effective in local abdominal adiposity reduction than HIIT sessions. This can be attributed to the different mechanisms of UC & RF and HIIT exercise in reduction of abdominal adiposity.

Also, these differences between both groups may be due to the conflict that HIIT exercise causes its fat burn effect on abdominal adiposity only in long interventions (>12 weeks), while the duration of the current study was 8 weeks. It was reported that duration of the interventions may be a relevant factor in generating more consistent results (31, 32). However, some studies have shown changes in body composition in short protocols of HIIT (3 and 6 weeks) (33, 34).

Regarding weight, BMI and body fat percentage, this study showed a statistically highly significant improvement (reduction) in both groups ($P < 0.001$). The reduction in group A was in agreement with results of several studies that reported statistically highly significant reduction ($P < 0.001$) in weight, body fat percentage and BMI after combined UC & RF and low caloric diet (17, 22, 23).

However, Abdel- Aal et al. 2022 study reported more weight loss (17.5 kg) and prominent reduction in BMI (6.48 Kg/m²) more than our results which could be due to longer duration of the session (RF 40 minutes, 50 minutes UC), different device used (EunSung Global Co Ltd., Seoul, Korea) and longer duration of follow up (3 months), which raise the idea that longer follow up could lead to further improvement in these parameters (23).

On the other hand, recent study reported less reduction in BMI (0.4 Kg/m²) than our study after four sessions of combined UC & RF which could be due to fewer number of sessions and their patients didn't followed any diet regimen (35).

The results of group B was in line with several studies that reported statistically significant reduction ($p < 0.05$) in body weight, BMI, body fat percentage and total fat mass after HIIT exercise (30, 32, 36).

On comparing group A and group B, our results revealed statistically highly significant difference ($P < 0.001$) between mean value of reduction as regards weight, BMI and body fat percentage. The reduction was more prominent in group B than group A. That's means that HIIT sessions were more effective in reducing total body weight, BMI and reducing total body fat more that combined UC & RF sessions.

HIIT exercise has superior mechanism for total fat loss mainly linked to changes in excess post-exercise oxygen consumption (EPOC), greater fat oxidation and changes in appetite and satiety mechanisms by reducing average TNF-Alpha, Peptide YY(PYY), and Ghrelin concentrations, and increasing GLP-1 (37). In this study, patients also were on balanced hypo-caloric diet together with powerful effect of HIIT exercise on EPOC cause greater weight loss.

Regarding blood pressure, there was highly statistically significant reduction (P value <0.001) in SBP & DBP in both groups. In group A, 4 patients became normal as regards SBP and 13 patients became normal as regards DBP after eight sessions of combined UC & RF. This agrees with the results reported by Farag et al in 2021 who also noticed a decrease in both systolic and diastolic blood pressure after 8 sessions of UC (28).

This drop in blood pressure could be explained by the improvement in different hemodynamic patterns, higher metabolic activity, raised activity of the sympathetic nervous system and the renin–angiotensin–aldosterone system that associated with abdominal obesity (38, 39).

In our study group B, 18 patients became normal as regards SBP and the 20 patients of the group became normal as regards DBP after HIIT sessions. This in agreement with recent study that used the same HIIT protocol we used, reported significant reduction in SBP and DBP (40).

On comparing group A and group B, there was more apparent reduction in SBP & DBP in group B than group A. That suggests that HIIT sessions were more effective in reducing systolic and diastolic blood pressure.

The most sensitive MetS variables to HIIT exercise are SBP and DBP, thus researchers suggest that HIIT exercise can be used among lines of treatment for hypertension. (41, 42, 43). HIIT exercise have superior mechanisms for these reductions in blood pressure which are enhancement of baroreflex control of the sympathetic nerve activity, reduction in total peripheral resistance, reduction of catecholamines (norepinephrine) in circulation and changes in vasodilator and vasoconstrictor factors (37).

Regarding lipid profile in our study, there was a highly significant improvement in lipid profile in both groups. This reduction in group A is in agreement with the study done Ahmed et al. 2018 and El Gendy et al. 2017. However, in El Gendy et al. 2017 there was more prominent reduction than our study which could be explained by larger number of UC sessions received (16 sessions) together with low caloric diet (1200- 1500 cal/day) & abdominal exercise (3 times per week) for eight consecutive weeks (44, 45).

That improvement in lipid profile could be due to the significant reduction in body fat mass and abdominal fat mass which is more strongly related to lipid /lipoprotein abnormalities (46, 47). Fat metabolites from cavitation processed in the liver in the same manner as fat originating from digested fat, both are expelled via the urinary system (48).

On the other hand, previous studies reported absence of significant differences in lipid profile before & after treatment by UC (49, 50, 51). This disagreement with our results of lipid profile may be due to the different methods and parameters of UC. It could be also due to different timing of lipid profile investigation as the purpose of measuring lipid profile in those studies was to ensure safety of UC on lipid profile (44).

Two studies in 2021 showed more reduction in lipid profile than our study results of group B. That may be due to different HIIT protocol used by Hyun, 2021 consisted of 24 sessions (3

sessions per week for 8 weeks) of 20 seconds of exercise at 85–90% of HR-max followed by 30 seconds of exercise at 60% of HR-max, with (2 sets of 12 repetitions) (30) or due to longer duration of follow up in de Matos et al. 2021 study (12 weeks), which could suggest that longer interventions of HIIT exercise cause further improvement in lipid profile (40).

On comparing group A and group B as regards lipid profile. Our results revealed statistically highly significant difference (P value <0.001) regarding reduction in cholesterol level. The reduction was more prominent in group B than group A. The mechanism for this improvement of lipid profile after HIIT exercise could be related to a greater up-regulation for capacity of mitochondria to oxidize lipids following HIIT exercise (52).

Regarding glycemic control, there was statistically highly significant reduction in blood glucose level and HOMA-IR in both groups ($P <0.001$). A study was done by Youssef et al. 2019 documented prominent reduction than this study results of group A which could be explained by their patients received 12 sessions of UC, low caloric diet treatment, as well as aerobics exercise three times per weeks for twelve weeks (50). Fasting insulin reduction in group A is in concordance with Abdel-Aal et al study that reported highly significant reduction in fasting insulin by 3.66 mIU/ml after combined UC & RF and low caloric diet (23).

Results of group B as regards glycemic control was in line with the two studies in 2021 that reported statistically highly significant reduction in fasting glucose and fasting insulin after HIIT exercise sessions (30, 40).

On the other hand, in a study done by Haganes and his colleges in 2022 the results showed non-statistically significant reduction in fasting glucose, fasting insulin and HOMA-IR after HIIT exercise compared to control group. This disagreement may be due to the use of two different HIIT protocols every week and different duration, they used HIIT protocol 3 sessions per weeks for 7 weeks (Two of the sessions were 4×4 min HIIT and one session was 10×1 min HIIT every week) (53).

On comparing group A and group B as regards glycemic control and insulin resistance. Our results revealed statistically highly significant difference ($P < 0.001$) regarding reduction in fasting glucose and HOMA-IR. The reduction was more prominent in group B than group A. That's means a highly significant improvement in insulin resistance after HIIT exercise sessions more than after UC & RF sessions.

That significant reduction observed in blood glucose after HIIT exercise might be explained by increase in SMM, insulin receptors and blood flow along with increased disposal of glucose in the skeletal muscle by increase expression of GLUT-4 expression and greater recruitment of type II skeletal muscle fibers which may explain the fact that exercise intensity correlates positively with insulin sensitivity (54, 55).

Two previous studies documented that six sessions of low-volume HIIT 10×1 at 90% HRmax (our same protocol) performed over two weeks, led to increased mitochondrial protein content,

elevated mitochondrial enzyme capacity and reduced hyperglycemia (56, 57). Recent study demonstrated the effect of 12 weeks of low-volume HIIT (10×1 -min at $\sim 90\%$ HRmax) on muscle insulin sensitivity and reported increased glycogen storage after HIIT exercise (58). The increase of basal capacity of skeletal muscle to store glycogen cause the longer-term insulin sensitizing effects of exercise (59).

Regarding MPV, There was a highly statistically significant reduction in both groups. On comparing group A and group B, there was statistically highly significant difference ($P < 0.001$) as regards mean value of reduction. There was a prominent reduction in group B more than group A.

Improvement in more components of metabolic syndrome in group B than in group A could explain the prominent reduction of MPV in group B than group A. There was obvious reduction in fasting glucose, in triglyceride and in blood pressure in group B than group A as a recent study showed a significant correlation was observed between MPV and MetS and between MPV and the number of components of MetS (60).

Another explanation is that prominent reduction in body fat percentage, fasting glucose and improvement in insulin resistance in group B than group A. As Met S patients who have high adipose tissue level, which secretes various adipokines and cytokines, cause megakaryocytes to produce larger platelets (61, 62). Hyperglycemia that leads to osmotic swelling of platelet and elevated MPV (63). Also, insulin resistance is a crucial mechanism underlying MetS and positively correlated MPV. So, insulin resistance may be considered the plausibly link between MPV and MetS (60).

This is the first study to compare effect of combined UC & RF versus HIIT exercise on anthropometric indices and on other metabolic syndrome variables such as blood pressure, dyslipidemia and insulin resistance. Also, this is the first study to show the effect of combined UC & RF on MPV and the effect of HIIT exercise on MPV in metabolic syndrome patients as an important biomarker of different risk factors on metabolic health.

5. LIMITATION OF THE STUDY:

This study examined a limited sample size; therefore, large sample size is required in future studies. Also, the effects of UC & RF versus HIIT on MetS variables were measured after 8 weeks follow up in the current study. So, Longer term follow up should be conducted to ensure long-term effects of both interventions.

Moreover, although skinfold thickness and waist circumference are valid, reliable, and cost-effective measurements of adipose thickness, ultrasound, computerized tomography, and magnetic resonance imaging are objective measurements of adipose thickness and might add a great value in future studies

6 .CONCLUSIONS

This current study supports that combined UC & RF sessions are very effective in reducing abdominal obesity and improvement in other MetS variables such as dyslipidemia, hypertension, hyperglycemia and insulin resistance. However, HIIT exercise was superior in reducing total body weight, total body fat, BMI and superior in reducing blood pressure, MPV, cholesterol level, blood glucose level and improving insulin resistance more than combined UC & RF. Also, This study confirms positive correlation between MPV and waist circumference, weight, WHR, BMI, skin fold thickness, abdominal fat range, body fat Percentage, systolic blood pressure, diastolic blood pressure, cholesterol, TG, LDL, Cholesterol: HDL ratio, fasting glucose, fasting insulin and HOMA-IR and negative correlation between MPV and HDL before and after treatment in all patients. This means that MPV can be a diagnostic and also prognostic biomarker for all these risk factors and useful in longitudinal studies.

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CONFLICT OF INTERESTS

There are no conflicts of interest for the writers.

LIST OF ABBREVIATION:

- Body mass index (BMI)
- Diastolic blood pressure DBP
- Excess post-exercise oxygen consumption (EPOC),
- High-intensity interval training (HIIT)
- High-density lipoprotein cholesterol (HDL-C).
- (HOMA-IR) Homeostatic Model Assessment for Insulin Resistance
- Low-density lipoprotein cholesterol (LDL-C).
- Mean platelet volume (MPV)
- Peptide YY (PYY)
- Radiofrequency (RF)
- skeletal muscle mass (SMM)
- Systolic blood pressure SBP
- Triglyceride (TG)
- Tumor necrosis factor (TNF)
- Ultrasonic Cavitation (UC)

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- Visceral fat range (VFR)
 - Waist to hip ratio (WHR)

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